

Implementing UAVs in Smart Cities: Use Cases and Challenges

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Abstract—In recent years, with the advanced development of smart cities, the integration of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) has become crucial due to their numerous benefits across various fields, such as traffic management, surveillance operations, delivery services, emergency response, and agricultural monitoring. This study explores the diverse types and applications of UAVs used in smart cities to enhance the quality of life for their residents. It also focuses on the role of UAVs in improving the efficiency and functionality of these cities. By using UAVs, cities can achieve improved traffic flow, better emergency response capabilities, and more efficient surveillance systems. However, this integration is not without challenges. Technical limitations include issues related to navigation, communication, speed, and privacy. Additionally, non-technical limitations such as safety concerns, privacy issues, and the costs associated with UAV development and construction pose significant challenges. Despite these challenges, advancements in UAV technology promise a future of autonomous, intelligent applications that can significantly enhance urban living.

Index Terms—Unmanned Aerial Vehicle, Smart City, Urban Living, UAV Challenges, UAV Applications,

I. INTRODUCTION

The integration of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) into smart cities represents a significant technological advancement. These smart cities' role is to improve residents' lives with innovative solutions, and UAVs are the perfect fit. These drones can provide real-time information in situations such as transportation, traffic jams, surveillance, pollution levels, emergency response, and environmental monitoring [1]. In transportation services, these UAVs provide efficient delivery services, which reduces pollution and traffic congestion. In surveillance applications, UAVs are used for real-time monitoring, which ensures public safety and aids different law agencies [2]. In addition, UAVs play a crucial role in environmental monitoring, which has the ability to collect different data such as air quality, pollution and noise levels, and climate conditions. Moreover, UAVs offer rapid assessment and support and enhance the efficiency of rescue operations in emergency response missions. The integration of UAVs into smart cities underscores their transformative potential, promoting efficiency, safety, and sustainability in urban environments [3]. Despite the promising applications of UAVs, their integration into smart cities has numerous challenges, such as limitations related to traffic management and privacy,

as well as technical challenges, such as flight time, battery life, payload capacity, and communication. UAVs in smart cities must be integrated with other systems, such as manipulation tasks, including grasping and releasing objects [4]. This paper aims to identify the challenges associated with current and future UAV applications in smart cities and propose solutions. We have conducted this study to ensure it aligns with our article's objectives. The following sections include a review of related work, a discussion of different UAV types and their applications within a smart city, also an examination of the significant challenges UAVs face in this environment.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 briefly describes the literature review on using UAVs in smart cities, and Section 3 details the different types of UAVs. Section 4 describes the UAV applications, and Section 5 presents the different challenges. The conclusion is presented in Section 6.

II. RELATED WORKS

Extensive research has been conducted in recent years on integrating UAVs in smart cities. Several studies have focused on specific applications, highlighting their potential benefits and addressing various challenges. To solve problems related to insufficient energy and computing resources. Researchers propose many solutions and improve existing ones [5]. Fotouhi et al. [6] examined the role of UAVs in enhancing the cyber-physical security of cellular communication systems. They also highlight the new business opportunities for cellular operators from UAVs, such as user equipment and flying base stations. Bagloee et al. [7] explore the challenges and opportunities of autonomous vehicle technologies (AV). They review safety, ethics, and routing behaviors. In addition, they also propose a navigation model for centrally dispatched AV fleets to optimize traffic efficiency. Butilă et al. [8] systematically review UAV applications in civil engineering, focusing on traffic monitoring. the paper explores emerging trends and potential benefits which underscores advancements in UAV technology and image processing for future applications. Adam et al. [9] examine the historical evolution and current urban air mobility (UAM) advancements through interviews and workshops, detailing its phases and addressing regulatory, safety, noise, equity, and environmental challenges. they conclude by proposing future research directions in UAM, focusing

on sustainability, societal impacts, airspace integration, and business models. Hemamalini et al. [10] address research gaps by designing a Smart Drone to monitor nine pollutants in metropolitan areas. They focus on solid waste dump yards. Real-time data trains a bidirectional gated recurrent unit (Bi-GRU) network model. Edwin et al. [11] explore the multifaceted roles of drones in future smart cities, addressing concerns in cybersecurity, privacy, and public safety. Xiaodong et al. [12] introduce a novel approach for sustainable data processing in multi-drone smart city networks, using edge computing to achieve energy-efficient and low-latency analysis of data closer to its source, addressing challenges like congestion and collision in smart city environments. Kumar et al. [13] explore the integration of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) in smart farming. They highlight the role of Bluetooth Low Energy for cost-effective UAV control via smartphones. The study also discusses various sensor types, operational requirements, challenges, and future applications of UAVs in agricultural contexts.

III. UAV DIFFERENT TYPES

UAVs, also known as drones, are operated without a human pilot using specific algorithms for obstacle avoidance and fly autonomously to do specific tasks. Different types of UAVs with different shapes have been used in smart city structures (Fig.1). This section will discuss each type and highlight their advantages and limitations in specific roles.

Fig. 1: Different Types of UAVs Used in Smart City Structures

A. Fixed-Wing

Fixed-wing UAVs use a fixed wing for lift. These types have longer distances and flight times. Fixed-wing UAVs can cover larger areas, making them suitable for tasks like surveillance, delivery, and aerial mapping. However, they face challenges such as stability issues in winds. In addition, they generally require more complex planning and control systems, especially for autonomous operations. Despite these challenges, fixed-wing UAVs remain a crucial component of modern UAV technology, offering advantages for applications that require efficiency, speed, and long-endurance capabilities [7].

B. Rotary-Wing

Rotary-wing UAVs, or multi-rotors, use multiple rotors to generate lift and control their movement. Due to their agility, stability, and versatility, these types are used in smart city applications such as Aerial Photography, videography, and surveillance. They also have excellent maneuverability, which can hover in place, fly sideways, rotate on the spot, and perform other agile movements. This makes them ideal for tasks requiring precise positioning and close-range inspections. In addition, Rotary-Wing UAVs can take off and land vertically (VTOL), making them highly versatile in various environments. However, they face limitations such as short-time flight and payload capacity [14].

C. Single-Rotors

This is a special case in rotary-wing UAVs, which use a main rotor to fly and others in the tail to provide stability and control, such as helicopters. These UAVs are generally more efficient than multirotor UAVs, offering longer flight times and the ability to carry heavier payloads. However, the larger rotor blades pose a greater safety risk, both in terms of potential damage to property and harm to people in the event of an accident [15].

D. Fixed-wing hybrid VTOL drones

These types of drones combine the advantages of fixed-wing and rotary-wing UAVs. They can take off and land vertically like a single-rotor UAV and fly horizontally like a fixed-wing UAV. These drones typically have rotors and a fixed wing. the first one lifts the UAV, allowing it to take off and hover. and the second one is used for the horizontal flight when UAV reaches a certain altitude. fixed-wing hybrid VTOL UAVs are much more efficient and can cover greater distances than fixed-wings and rotary wings [16].

Tab.I presents a comparison of various UAVs across different characteristics.

IV. UAV APPLICATIONS IN SMART CITIES

With the later advancements in UAVs, this field opens up various opportunities [18]. Different drones can be utilized based on the task or mission requirement. UAVs are considered to have significant advantages in several areas, especially in public safety, rescue operations, and product delivery [19]. These UAVs can also help with forest fire alarms and deliver medical supplies to inaccessible places. These operations are done with the help of different sensors. Tab.II presents an overview of various sensing devices used in UAVs. UAV applications significantly enhance smart city services by optimizing data collection and analysis, improving infrastructure management, boosting efficiency, and enhancing emergency services [21]. This section briefly examines the roles of UAVs in various applications within smart cities.

Characteristics	Fixed Wing	Rotary Wing	Single Rotor	Hybrid VTOL
Flight System	Complicated	Simple	Simple	Complicated
Power Supply	Battery, Fuel	Battery	Battery	Battery, Fuel
Energy Efficiency	High	Low	Medium	High
Landing	Conventional	Vertical	Vertical	Vertical
Autonomy	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Hovering	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Endurance	1- 24 hours	0.5-2 hours	0.5-4 hours	3-8 hours
Payload	100 kg	50 kg	30 kg	15 kg
Weight	0.1-400,000 kg	0.01-100 kg	0.5-10 kg	1.5-65 kg
Cost	High	Medium	Low	Medium
Maintenance	High	Low	Medium	Medium
Speed	High	Medium	Low	Medium
Maneuverability	Low	High	Medium	High
Range	Long	Short	Medium	Long
Noise Level	Low	High	Medium	Medium

TABLE I: Comparison of UAV Characteristics [20]

Fig. 2: UAV Applications In Smart Cities

A. Delivery Services

With recent advancements and the challenges in delivery services, UAVs have been utilized as delivery agents, playing a crucial role in enhancing the functionality and efficiency of smart cities. Drones are increasingly used for last-mile delivery of parcels, medical supplies, and other goods. They offer a fast and efficient solution for urban logistics, especially in hard-to-reach areas. [22].

B. Traffic management and monitoring

Traffic congestion is a significant issue in smart cities. This issue arises from various factors such as peak hours, major events, construction activities, or accidents [23], which impact mobility, air quality, and overall quality of life. UAVs play a crucial role in addressing this challenge by providing real-time traffic data, monitoring congestion, and detecting accidents. This information helps city planners and traffic management systems optimize traffic flow, reduce congestion, and enhance overall transportation efficiency. By offering a comprehensive

and dynamic view of traffic patterns, UAVs enable more effective traffic signal control, route planning, and incident management, ultimately contributing to smoother and safer urban transportation in smart cities.

C. Agricultural Monitoring

The use of drones in the agricultural field is necessary due to the live data and imagery of crops and fields. UAVs can be equipped with different sensors, such as multispectral, thermal, and RGB cameras, to capture detailed information about soil conditions, crop health, irrigation efficiency, and pest infestations. Moreover, UAVs can aid in monitoring crop growth to assess optimal harvesting times or identify the necessity for protective measures. Using these drones for early detection enables farmers to act more quickly and avoid associated risks [23]. As a result, Applying UAVs in agriculture offers farmers innovative tools to increase their productivity compared to traditional ways, reduce farming costs, and minimize environmental impact.

D. Entertainment

In the entertainment field, the absence of UAVs poses several challenges. The first is limited access to aerial shots. In addition, without using UAVs, productions rely heavily on traditional methods such as using helicopters or cranes, which can be highly expensive, time-consuming to set up, and more dangerous to the crew members. Moreover, tracking and taking high-res images and videos of objects can be highly costly, such as touristic videos, dangerous animals in a jungle, and high-risk places. UAVs are the most efficient solution to these challenges, as they can easily take high-res photos and videos with the help of high-quality integrated cameras. Also, they can deliver promotional material such as banners, banners, and flyers. Overall, these drones make the Entertainment field more attractive with lower costs [18].

E. Remote Sensing

Data collection and analysis are highly important in smart city operations [24]. Remote sensing tasks based only on satellites and ground sensors are challenging. These sensors

TABLE II: UAV onboard sensors

Ref.	Sensors	Applications	Advantages	Limitations
[28]	Thermal infrared sensors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forest fires detection • Gas leak visualisation • Waterstress detection 	Low energy consumption, small size, small size, weather-resistant	limited distance, low accuracy, sunlight interference, indoor use only
[29]	Hyperspectral sensors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • hyperspectral exploration • Detection of disaster damage • Agriculture management • Fire risk analysis 	Better image quality, high classification accuracy, flexible operation, wide coverage	Hyperspectral cost, more complex, Big storage resources are required
[30]	Light detection and ranging (LiDAR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building data and information • Cultural heritage mapping • Absorption analysis • Forest carbon estimation • Vegetation canopy analysis 	high image resolution, feasible for spatial classification, access to inaccessible Locations, penetration capabilities	impact of vehicle mobility, cost concerns, altitude Limitations
[31]	GPS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Surveying and sapping • Navigation • Tracking and recreation 	Low power, low costs, small size, high precision	signal loss, orbital errors, delays, affected by magnetic environment

often struggle to match the spatial resolution and flexibility of UAVs. Ground-based sensors face limitations when accessing inaccessible areas, such as dense forests or disaster zones, because they can't penetrate obstacles in their way, where UAVs can maneuver effectively. In addition, using satellites for these tasks faces constraints like weather conditions, limited window times, and higher costs, which impact data availability, especially in emergencies, and temporal resolution [25]. Integrating UAVs for these operations is crucial due to their ability to overcome these challenges by providing faster, high-resolution, and adaptable platforms for remote sensing applications across various fields [26].

V. CHALLENGES OF UAVS IN SMART CITIES

While UAVs provide numerous advantages and positive impacts on smart cities, they also face multiple challenges and limitations. These challenges can be classified into two main categories: technical challenges, such as navigation, security, safety, speed, and communication, and non-technical challenges, such as privacy laws, ethical consideration, licensing, and costs [3]. This section outlines the diverse challenges of integrating UAVs in smart city operations.

A. Technical Challenges

1) *Speed*: While UAVs enhance delivery services by providing faster delivery times, their high speeds can pose dangers to the environment and threaten public safety, especially when operated in densely populated areas [27]. Conversely, using lower speeds results in longer delivery times. Similar scenarios apply in other fields, such as monitoring, surveillance, and filmography.

2) *Security*: One of the biggest challenges facing UAVs is security concerns. These drones are highly vulnerable to external intrusions and attacks. For example, imagine a scenario

where a UAV in a populated area gets hacked. This attack could cause damage to humans or property. Another scenario is when a UAV is collecting sensitive data, and this data gets compromised, posing a matter of national security [32]. So, ensuring the security of these drones is crucial to avoiding accidents and ensuring public safety. This involves certifying UAVs and operators and setting up protocols for emergencies.

3) *Navigation*: Path planning and navigation for UAVs in smart cities are complex tasks due to urban environments, especially with moving obstacles such as humans, cars, and birds, considering weather conditions. Hence, UAVs require advanced collision avoidance algorithms and efficient path planning algorithms to navigate safely and efficiently, avoiding threats in their way regarding environmental factors [2].

4) *Communication*: Using UAVs in smart city operations requires reliable communications between them and the ground base, or missions require collaboration. So there is a need for strong secured communication channels to ensure better contact, safety, and security against external threats [33]. These communications must meet specific quality of service (QoS) standards, including adequate bandwidth, low delay, high transfer rates, and minimal jitter. Different communication architectures are employed, such as direct link, satellite link, cellular architecture, and mesh network. Each technique with unique advantages and limitations [34].

B. Non-Technical Challenges

1) *Privacy*: Integrating sensors and cameras in UAVs and using them to collect data in different operations for smart cities may raise privacy concerns regarding individuals' privacy rights by capturing sensitive information without authorisation. Addressing these concerns requires strict regulations governing data collection, storage, and usage to protect against unauthorized surveillance and ensure transparency in how

collected data is handled. In some countries, such as the United Kingdom, their residents are protected by the Data Protection Act. Gavoukian et al. [35] discuss numerous privacy challenges related to UAV operations and offer solutions for addressing these issues.

2) *Ethical Considerations:* UAVs in smart cities are employed for various applications and are managed by a diversity of public and private organizations. These drones raise concerns regarding surveillance, data privacy, and the potential misuse of collected information, which could divert them from their intended purposes. For instance, they might be used for spying on individuals or entities or gathering data to influence specific organizations [36]. Therefore, developing a code of ethics is crucial for the secure utilization of UAVs in smart cities.

3) *Cost:* Developing UAV projects involves significant costs, which can be even higher when specific designs for specialized roles are needed. For example, creating UAVs capable of carrying people, such as UAV taxis or UAV ambulances, incurs substantial expenses. Another example is investing in new projects with advanced technologies and designs, such as sensors, cameras, and rotors. Additionally, ongoing expenses, including maintenance, software updates, and operator training, contribute to the overall cost [37]. Balancing these costs with the anticipated advantages is crucial for the sustainable deployment of UAVs in smart cities

VI. CONCLUSION

Integrating UAVs in smart city applications offers numerous benefits, such as improving traffic management, developing and enhancing surveillance operations, creating efficient delivery services, and more. This study discusses different types and applications of UAVs to enhance smart cities, such as delivery services, emergency response operations, traffic management and agricultural monitoring, and entertainment services. However, this integration causes several challenges, including technical limitations in navigation and communication, speed and privacy, non-technical limitations regarding safety and privacy, and the significant costs associated with development and deployment. Despite these challenges, the integration of UAVs opens up vast opportunities for advanced, autonomous, and intelligent applications across various fields and domains.

VII. DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTEREST

The authors declare that there are no financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Mohamed, N., Al-Jaroodi, J., Jawhar, I., Idries, A., & Mohammed, F. (2020). Unmanned aerial vehicles applications in future smart cities. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 153, 119293. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.TECHFORE.2018.05.004>
- [2] Abbas, N., Abbas, Z., Liu, X., Khan, S. S., Foster, E. D., & Larkin, S. (2023). A Survey: Future Smart Cities Based on Advance Control of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs). *Applied Sciences* 2023, Vol. 13, Page 9881, 13(17), 9881. <https://doi.org/10.3390/AP13179881>
- [3] AL-Dosari, K., & Fetais, N. (2023). A New Shift in Implementing Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) in the Safety and Security of Smart Cities: A Systematic Literature Review. *Safety* 2023, Vol. 9, Page 64, 9(3), 64. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SAFETY9030064>
- [4] Mohammed, F., Idries, A., Mohamed, N., Al-Jaroodi, J., & Jawhar, I. (2014). UAVs for smart cities: Opportunities and challenges. 2014 International Conference on Unmanned Aircraft Systems, ICUAS 2014 - Conference Proceedings, 267–273. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICUAS.2014.6842265>
- [5] Naqvi, S. A. R., Hassan, S. A., Pervaiz, H., & Ni, Q. (2018). Drone-Aided Communication as a Key Enabler for 5G and Resilient Public Safety Networks. *IEEE Communications Magazine*, 56(1), 36–42. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCOM.2017.1700451>
- [6] Fotouhi, A., Qiang, H., Ding, M., Hassan, M., Giordano, L. G., Garcia-Rodriguez, A., & Yuan, J. (2019). Survey on UAV Cellular Communications: Practical Aspects, Standardization Advancements, Regulation, and Security Challenges. *IEEE Communications Surveys and Tutorials*, 21(4), 3417–3442. <https://doi.org/10.1109/COMST.2019.2906228>
- [7] Bagloee, S.A., Taviana, M., Asadi, M. et al. Autonomous vehicles: challenges, opportunities, and future implications for transportation policies. *J. Mod. Transport.* 24, 284–303 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40534-016-0117-3>
- [8] Butilă, E. V., & Boboc, R. G. (2022). Urban Traffic Monitoring and Analysis Using Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs): A Systematic Literature Review. *Remote Sensing* 2022, Vol. 14, Page 620, 14(3), 620. <https://doi.org/10.3390/RS14030620>
- [9] Cohen, A. P., Shaheen, S. A., & Farrar, E. M. (2021). Urban Air Mobility: History, Ecosystem, Market Potential, and Challenges. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 22(9), 6074–6087. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TITS.2021.3082767>
- [10] Rani Hemamalini, R., Vinodhini, R., Shanthini, B., Partheeban, P., Charumathy, M., & Cornelius, K. (2022). Air quality monitoring and forecasting using smart drones and recurrent neural network for sustainable development in Chennai city. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 85, 104077. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.SCS.2022.104077>
- [11] Vattapparamban, E., Güvenç, I., Yurekli, A. I., Akkaya, K., & Uluagaç, S. (2016). Drones for smart cities: Issues in cybersecurity, privacy, and public safety. 2016 International Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing Conference, IWCMC 2016, 216–221. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IWCMC.2016.7577060>
- [12] Ren, X., Vashisht, S., Aujla, G. S., & Zhang, P. (2022). Drone-Edge Coalesce for Energy-Aware and Sustainable Service Delivery for Smart City Applications. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 77, 103505. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.SCS.2021.103505>
- [13] Reddy Maddikunta, P. K., Hakak, S., Alazab, M., Bhattacharya, S., Gadekallu, T. R., Khan, W. Z., & Pham, Q. V. (2021). Unmanned Aerial Vehicles in Smart Agriculture: Applications, Requirements, and Challenges. *IEEE Sensors Journal*, 21(16), 17608–17619. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JSEN.2021.3049471>
- [14] Cai, G., Lum, K. Y., Chen, B. M., & Lee, T. H. (2010). A brief overview on miniature fixed-wing unmanned aerial vehicles. 2010 8th IEEE International Conference on Control and Automation, ICCA 2010, 285–290. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCA.2010.5524453>
- [15] Ucgun, H., Yuzgec, U., & Bayilmis, C. (2021). A review on applications of rotary-wing unmanned aerial vehicle charging stations. *International Journal of Advanced Robotic Systems*, 18(3). <https://doi.org/10.1177/17298814211015863>
- [16] Qi, X., Qi, J., Theilliol, D., Zhang, Y., Han, J., Song, D., & Hua, C. (2014). A review on fault diagnosis and fault tolerant control methods for single-rotor aerial vehicles. *Journal of Intelligent and Robotic Systems: Theory and Applications*, 73(1–4), 535–555. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S10846-013-9954-Z/METRICS>
- [17] Zhou, M., Zhou, Z., Liu, L., Huang, J., & Lv, Z. (2018). Review of vertical take-off and landing fixed-wing UAV and its application prospect

- in precision agriculture. *International Journal of Precision Agricultural Aviation*, 1(1), 8–17. <https://doi.org/10.33440/IJPA.20200304.130>
- [18] Gupta, A., Afrin, T., Scully, E., & Yodo, N. (2021). Advances of UAVs toward Future Transportation: The State-of-the-Art, Challenges, and Opportunities. *Future Transportation* 2021, Vol. 1, Pages 326-350, 1(2), 326–350. <https://doi.org/10.3390/FUTURETRANSP1020019>
- [19] Lagkas, T., Argyriou, V., Bibi, S., & Sarigiannidis, P. (2018). UAV IoT Framework Views and Challenges: Towards Protecting Drones as “Things.” *Sensors* 2018, Vol. 18, Page 4015, 18(11), 4015. <https://doi.org/10.3390/S18114015>
- [20] Çakici, F., & Leblebicioğlu, M. K. (2016). Analysis of a UAV that can Hover and Fly Level. *MATEC Web of Conferences*, 59, 07010. <https://doi.org/10.1051/MATECCONF/20165907010>
- [21] Yigitcanlar, T., Desouza, K. C., Butler, L., & Roozkhosh, F. (2020). Contributions and Risks of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Building Smarter Cities: Insights from a Systematic Review of the Literature. *Energies* 2020, Vol. 13, Page 1473, 13(6), 1473. <https://doi.org/10.3390/EN13061473>
- [22] Betti Sorbelli, F. (2024). UAV-Based Delivery Systems: A Systematic Review, Current Trends, and Research Challenges. *Journal on Autonomous Transportation Systems*, 1(3), 1–40. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3649224>
- [23] Shah, S. F. A., Mazhar, T., Shloul, T. al, Shahzad, T., Hu, Y. C., Mallek, F., & Hamam, H. (2024). Applications, challenges, and solutions of unmanned aerial vehicles in smart city using blockchain. *PeerJ Computer Science*, 10, 1–35. <https://doi.org/10.7717/PEERJ-CS.1776>
- [24] al Nuaimi, E., al Neyadi, H., Mohamed, N., & Al-Jaroodi, J. (2015). Applications of big data to smart cities. *Journal of Internet Services and Applications*, 6(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/S13174-015-0041-5/FIGURES/3>
- [25] Laliberte, A. S., Goforth, M. A., Steele, C. M., & Rango, A. (2011). Multispectral Remote Sensing from Unmanned Aircraft: Image Processing Workflows and Applications for Rangeland Environments. *Remote Sensing* 2011, Vol. 3, Pages 2529-2551, 3(11), 2529–2551. <https://doi.org/10.3390/RS3112529>
- [26] Maes, W. H., & Steppe, K. (2019). Perspectives for Remote Sensing with Unmanned Aerial Vehicles in Precision Agriculture. *Trends in Plant Science*, 24(2), 152–164. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TPLANTS.2018.11.007>
- [27] Cherif, N., Jaafar, W., Yanikomeroglu, H., & Yongacoglu, A. (2021). 3D Aerial Highway: The Key Enabler of the Retail Industry Transformation. *IEEE Communications Magazine*, 59(9), 65–71. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCOM.010.2100072>
- [28] Hill, A. C., Laugier, E. J., & Casana, J. (2020). Archaeological Remote Sensing Using Multi-Temporal, Drone-Acquired Thermal and Near Infrared (NIR) Imagery: A Case Study at the Enfield Shaker Village, New Hampshire. *Remote Sensing* 2020, Vol. 12, Page 690, 12(4), 690. <https://doi.org/10.3390/RS12040690>
- [29] Yang, B., Wang, S., Li, S., Zhou, B., Zhao, F., Ali, F., & He, H. (2022). Research and application of UAV-based hyperspectral remote sensing for smart city construction. *Cognitive Robotics*, 2, 255–266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.COGR.2022.12.002>
- [30] Lin, Y. C., Cheng, Y. T., Zhou, T., Ravi, R., Hasheminasab, S. M., Flatt, J. E., Troy, C., & Habib, A. (2019). Evaluation of UAV LiDAR for Mapping Coastal Environments. *Remote Sensing* 2019, Vol. 11, Page 2893, 11(24), 2893. <https://doi.org/10.3390/RS11242893>
- [31] Liu, Z., Zhang, Y., Yu, X., & Yuan, C. (2016). Unmanned surface vehicles: An overview of developments and challenges. *Annual Reviews in Control*, 41, 71–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ARCONTROL.2016.04.018>
- [32] Nassi, B., Shabtai, A., Masuoka, R., & Elovici, Y. (2019). SoK - Security and Privacy in the Age of Drones: Threats, Challenges, Solution Mechanisms, and Scientific Gaps. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1903.05155v1>
- [33] Tortonesi, M., Stefanelli, C., Benvegna, E., Ford, K., Suri, N., & Linderman, M. (2012). Multiple-UAV coordination and communications in tactical edge networks. *IEEE Communications Magazine*, 50(10), 48–55. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MCOM.2012.6316775>
- [34] Frew, E. W., & Brown, T. X. (2008). Airborne Communication Networks for Small Unmanned Aircraft Systems. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 96(12), 2008–2027. <https://doi.org/10.1109/JPROC.2008.2006127>
- [35] Cavoukian, A., & Kursawe, K. (2012). Implementing Privacy by Design: The smart meter case. 2012 IEEE International Conference on Smart Grid Engineering, SGE 2012. <https://doi.org/10.1109/SGE.2012.6463977>
- [36] Finn, R. L., & Wright, D. (2012). Unmanned aircraft systems: Surveillance, ethics and privacy in civil applications. *Computer Law & Security Review*, 28(2), 184–194. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CLSR.2012.01.005>
- [37] Malone, P., Apgar, H., Stukes, S., & Sterk, S. (2013). Unmanned Aerial Vehicles unique cost estimating requirements. *IEEE Aerospace Conference Proceedings*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/AERO.2013.6496852>